

Thermal Stability of *o*-Xylene-formaldehyde Resin and its Derivatives

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Nitrated and chlorinated derivatives of *o*-xylene-formaldehyde (*o*-XF) resin were prepared and the products were characterized by ir and nmr spectra. The average molecular weight of the substituted resin samples was determined by vapour pressure osmometry. Kinetic parameters were determined by differential thermal analysis, thermogravimetry and differential scanning calorimetry.

IN continuation of our previous work^{1,2} on the synthesis and thermal properties of xylene-formaldehyde resins, some derivatives of *o*-xylene-formaldehyde resin have been prepared and their thermal behaviour studied.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of analytical grade. *o*-Xylene-formaldehyde (*o*-XF) resin was prepared using *o*-xylene and paraformaldehyde with *p*-toluenesulphonic acid as catalyst. The experimental conditions for nitration and chlorination of *o*-XF resin were the same as those applied to *p*-xylene-formaldehyde resin². The experimental details for characterization of the samples are also the same as reported earlier.

Results and Discussion

Characterization :

The parent *o*-XF resin had a melting range around 113°, number average molecular weight ($\bar{M}_n$) of 1000 and heat of fusion, ΔH_f , of 0.02 kJ g⁻¹. Nitrated *o*-XF resin was yellow amorphous solid with 3.8% nitrogen. It was insoluble in common organic solvent and did not melt upto 300°. The chlorinated *o*-XF resin was yellow amorphous solid with a melting range around 78°, $\bar{M}_n$ of 1476 and ΔH_f of 0.006 kJ g⁻¹.

The ir spectra of nitrated *o*-XF resin showed a strong absorption band at 1540 cm⁻¹ due to asymmetric stretching of the -NO₂ group and a peak at 1350 cm⁻¹ due to symmetric stretching of -NO₂ group. This clearly indicated the presence of nitro groups on aromatic nuclei.

Chlorinated *o*-XF resin showed a chemical shift at 4.8 ppm for methylene group attached to chlorine and aromatic ring. It confirmed the chlorination of methyl groups.

These results showed that the number of repeat unit in a chain of chlorinated *o*-XF resin was an average of 9 and the number of chlorine atom per molecule of this resin was about 12.

Thermal stability :

The kinetic parameters of *o*-XF resin and its derivatives obtained from TG thermogram at different heating rates (RH) and using the Chatterjee³ method are given in Tables 1a, 1b and 1c. Table 2 also represents the kinetic parameter obtained using Broido⁴, Anderson-Freeman⁵, and Flynn-Wall⁶ methods from TG curves obtained at different RH. When the *o*-XF resin was heated at different RH in the TG study, the degradation occurred in single stage with 100% weight loss. The decomposition started at ~320° and continued up to ~635°. The activation energy, E_A , obtained from TG study using the Chatterjee method for decomposition, range from ~121.41 to ~133.97 kJ mol⁻¹. The Anderson-Freeman method gave an E_A in the range of ~87.92 to ~108.85 kJ mol⁻¹, while the E_A obtained from the Broido method varied from ~66.98 to ~113.04 kJ mol⁻¹. The Flynn-Wall method gave a higher E_A value compared to the other methods. In general, the decomposition followed first order kinetics.

The degradation of nitrated *o*-XF resin occurred in two stages. The major decomposition (~80%) took place in the second step. The decomposition started at ~210° and ended at ~610°. The E_A obtained from TG using the Chatterjee method for the first and second stages of decomposition ranged from ~41.86 to ~133.97 kJ mol⁻¹. The decomposition followed a first order kinetics for both the steps. The Anderson-Freeman method gave an E_A in the range of ~87.92 to ~100.48 kJ mol⁻¹ and that obtained from Broido method varied from ~62.80 to ~96.29 kJ mol⁻¹. E_A obtained from Flynn-Wall method was ~108.85 kJ mol⁻¹. In general, the decomposition followed first order kinetics.

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The degradation of chlorinated *o*-XF resin occurred in two steps when heated at different rates in TG. Major decomposition occurred with 70% weight loss in the second step. The E_A obtained using different method at different RH varied from

~33.49 to ~121.41 kJ mol⁻¹. The decomposition followed a first order kinetics for both the steps.

The kinetic parameters obtained from DTA curves using Reich⁷ and Kissinger⁸ methods are given in Table 3. The DTA thermograms of all

TABLE 1a—KINETIC PARAMETERS FROM TG THERMOGRAMS FOR *o*-XYLENE-FORMALDEHYDE RESIN

R.H.* °C min ⁻¹	Amount (mg)	Decomposition temperature range (°C)	ΔT (°C)	Weight loss (%)	E _A kJ mol ⁻¹	Order of reaction n	Frequency factor A ₀ min ⁻¹
6.5	50	320-635	315	100	138.55	1.3	8.86 × 10 ⁷
	25	325-630	310	100	138.55	1.3	9.18 × 10 ⁷
4.0	50	335-620	285	100	129.79	1.4	2.77 × 10 ⁷
	25	335-625	290	100	130.20	1.4	6.27 × 10 ⁷
2.5	50	340-620	280	100	126.03	1.0	2.01 × 10 ⁷
	25	340-615	275	100	127.69	1.0	3.68 × 10 ⁷
1.0	50	350-600	250	100	120.99	0.9	7.12 × 10 ⁷
	25	355-605	250	100	121.83	0.9	6.51 × 10 ⁶

Method : Chatterjee.
* Rate of heating.

TABLE 1b—KINETIC PARAMETERS FROM TG THERMOGRAM FOR NITRATED *o*-XF RESIN

R.H.* °C min ⁻¹	Amount (mg)	Decomposition temperature range (°C)	ΔT (°C)	Weight loss (%)	E _A kJ mol ⁻¹	Order of reaction n	Frequency factor A ₀ min ⁻¹
6.5	50	210-380	400	20	43.96	1.2	1.11 × 10 ⁶
		380-610		80	84.99	1.2	3.11 × 10 ⁶
	25	210-385	395	22	44.38	1.2	6.34 × 10 ⁶
4.0	50	385-605		78	85.41	1.2	4.18 × 10 ⁶
		215-380	385	19	50.24	1.0	1.2 × 10 ⁶
	25	360-600		81	87.08	1.1	3.37 × 10 ⁶
		215-350	385	20	56.52	1.0	2.50 × 10 ⁶
2.5	50	360-600		80	85.41	1.1	3.58 × 10 ⁶
		220-345	375	18	52.33	1.1	2.18 × 10 ⁶
	25	355-595		82	112.62	1.3	3.76 × 10 ⁶
		220-345	375	20	54.42	1.1	2.68 × 10 ⁶
1.0	50	355-595		80	109.69	1.3	2.15 × 10 ⁶
		240-340	310	20	48.56	1.0	3.68 × 10 ⁶
	25	350-550		80	133.14	1.4	3.33 × 10 ⁷
		240-340	310	20	51.07	1.0	4.98 × 10 ⁶
		350-550		80	131.04	1.4	4.88 × 10 ⁷

Method : Chatterjee.
* Rate of heating.

TABLE 1c—KINETIC PARAMETERS FROM TG THERMOGRAM FOR CHLORINATED *o*-XF RESIN

R.H.* °C min ⁻¹	Amount (mg)	Decomposition temperature range (°C)	ΔT (°C)	Weight loss (%)	E _A kJ mol ⁻¹	Order of reaction n	Frequency factor A ₀ min ⁻¹
6.5	50	140-310	450	30	33.49	1.2	8.20 × 10 ⁵
		310-590		70	75.36	1.6	3.36 × 10 ⁶
4.0	25	145-310	450	30	35.58	1.2	1.11 × 10 ⁴
		310-595		70	77.45	1.6	9.50 × 10 ⁵
	50	150-310	430	30	38.51	1.0	8.20 × 10 ⁵
		310-580		70	89.59	1.2	3.36 × 10 ⁶
2.5	25	150-310	430	30	38.93	1.0	1.11 × 10 ⁴
		310-580		70	87.92	1.2	9.50 × 10 ⁵
	50	155-300	400	25	49.40	1.0	3.46 × 10 ⁴
		310-555		75	102.57	1.1	3.93 × 10 ⁶
1.0	25	155-300	400	25	49.40	1.0	3.35 × 10 ⁴
		310-555		75	97.97	1.1	9.82 × 10 ⁵
	50	160-310	390	27	52.33	1.1	2.80 × 10 ⁵
		310-550		73	116.39	1.4	1.35 × 10 ⁷
	25	160-310	390	28	56.94	1.1	1.70 × 10 ⁴
		310-550		72	120.57	1.4	2.27 × 10 ⁷

Method : Chatterjee.
* Rate of heating.

TABLE 2—ENERGIES OF ACTIVATION (TG)

Resin	R.H. °C min ⁻¹	Amount of resin (mg)	Energy of activation, E _A (kJ mol ⁻¹)			n		
			Broido method	Anderson- Freeman method	Flynn- Wall method	Broido method	Anderson- Freeman method	
o-XF	6.5	50	67.82	98.88	127.27	1.0	1.0	
		25	71.59	88.76	128.95	1.0	1.1	
	4.0	50	75.78	99.64		1.0	1.2	
		25	77.03	100.48		1.0	1.3	
	2.5	50	90.43	104.67		1.0	1.2	
		25	90.01	105.50		1.0	1.2	
	1.0	50	111.36	108.43		1.0	1.2	
		25	113.04	108.85		1.0	1.1	
	Nitrated o-XF	6.5	50	61.54	87.92	110.95	1.0	1.3
			25	62.80	88.76	110.11	1.0	1.3
4.0		50	66.98	92.10		1.0	1.0	
		25	67.82	95.87		1.0	1.1	
2.5		50	77.03	98.38		1.0	0.8	
		25	77.03	100.06		1.0	0.9	
1.0		50	92.10	101.73		1.0	1.1	
		25	95.45	101.32		1.0	1.0	
Chlorinated o-XF		6.5	50	57.77	69.50	100.06	1.0	1.4
			25	58.19	70.33	102.99	1.0	1.5
	4.0	50	61.96	84.15		1.0	1.2	
		25	62.38	86.24		1.0	1.3	
	2.5	50	80.38	94.20		1.0	1.1	
		25	82.06	95.45		1.0	1.0	
	1.0	50	83.73	105.92		1.0	0.9	
		25	84.57	105.08		1.0	1.2	

TABLE 3—KINETIC PARAMETERS (DTA)

Resin	Rate of heating °C min ⁻¹	Peak temperature	E _A (kJ mol ⁻¹)	
			Reich	Kissinger
o-XF	6.5	525	120.57	83.78
	4.0	450	135.23	
	2.5	445	152.81	
	1.0	440	166.63	
Nitrated o-XF	6.5	375 (h)*	159.09	92.10
		525		
	4.0	360 (h)	167.89	
		510		
	2.5	350 (h)	185.47	
480				
1.0	325 (h)	184.21		
Chlorinated o-XF	6.5	395 (h)	150.72	106.76
		525		
	4.0	350 (h)	168.72	
		500		
	2.5	325 (h)	191.75	
475				
1.0	360 (h)	231.94		

* (h)=hump.

the three resin samples obtained at R.H. (a) 1.0°, (b) 2.5°, (c) 4.0° and (d) 6.5° min⁻¹ were exothermic in nature and all peaks were associated with humps (h) except in the case of o-XF resin.

The E_A values for o-XF resin obtained using Reich¹ method ranged from ~121.41 to ~167.47 kJ mol⁻¹ and the decomposition reaction followed nearly first order kinetics. The range of E_A for nitrated o-XF sample was from ~159.09 to ~184.21 kJ mol⁻¹ and followed nearly first order kinetics,

while the E_A values for the chlorinated o-XF sample ranged from ~150.72 to ~230.27 kJ mol⁻¹ and similar value (n) of the order of kinetics.

The E_A values for all the three resin samples obtained using the Kissinger² method had the trend : chlorinated o-XF (~108.85 kJ) > nitrated o-XF (~92.10 kJ) > o-XF (~83.73 kJ).

Summarising the kinetic parameters obtained from the TG curves (Tables 1a, 1b, 1c and 2) for all the three resin samples it is seen that the value of E_A increases with decrease in R.H. Similar behaviour was also observed in the case of DTA study. This might be due to the fact that the heat absorbed by the resin sample gets utilized in regrouping the molecules at lower heating rates. If the relaxation time, τ, is smaller than the time during which heat is delivered to the sample, the molecule will have time to regroup and the heat capacity will change gradually. At a high heating rate, the time for regrouping will be less and the heat is directly imparted to break the bonds in the molecules.

The E_A values obtained from the DTA study are higher in comparison to those obtained from the TG study. This could be ascribed to the retardation of decomposition of polymer sample, which is sandwiched between neutral media in a narrow cavity of DTA-microcell, compared to the decomposition in a shallow boat of the TG sample holder.

The kinetic data obtained from DTA curves using the methods of Reich and Kissinger :

The reich method deals with the energy of activation for a single thermogram obtained at a single

heating rate, whereas the Kissinger method involves many thermograms at different heating rate by keeping other experimental conditions constant. The exact experimental conditions except the heating rate is difficult to maintain and so the results are liable to permissible diversions. Apart from this the Kissinger method assumes that the energy of activation is the same for the decomposition of the sample at different heating rates. The Reich method is applicable only for distinct decomposition reaction and fails in the case of simultaneous reactions.

Comparing the results of E_A evaluated from TG by different methods, it may be said that the Chatterjee method assesses the order of reaction continuously throughout the pyrolysis range. This method is specially applicable to the complex reactions where it distinguishes the different decomposition reactions involved in an overall pyrolysis

process, which otherwise would not have been scrutinised. On the other hand, the indicated values of order of reaction are less sensitive and of considerable range and can be averaged with apparently little relation to weight changes or kinetic treatment.

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